

REHABILITATION PROGRAMS FOR PERSONS DEPRIVED OF LIBERTY (PDLs) IN NORTH COTABATO DISTRICT JAIL MALE AND FEMALE DORMITORIES

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ABSTRACT

Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) face numerous challenges during their incarceration, particularly regarding rehabilitation and reintegration into society. Rehabilitation programs are critical in addressing these challenges and ensuring the successful reintegration of PDLs into their communities. The quantitative descriptive-correlational research design was used. This study aimed to determine the demographic profile of the PDLs, the level of rehabilitation programs, if there was a significant relationship between the implementation level and the extent of problems encountered on the rehabilitation programs for the Persons Deprived of Liberty in North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories. This study found out that the implementation level of the rehabilitation programs is high and there was a significant relationship between the implementation level and the extent of issues encountered on the rehabilitation programs for PDLs. This study recommended increasing the fund support for rehabilitation programs, prioritize staff training for quality service delivery and improve jail facilities for a better learning environment. Moreover, expanding livelihood programs will provide marketable skills, while access to educational resources is essential for academic growth. Structured recreational activities can foster camaraderie and fitness. Finally, implementing a robust monitoring and evaluation framework will ensure ongoing assessment and improvements, and aiding successful reintegration into society.

Keywords: *implementation level, rehabilitation programs, persons deprived of liberty*

INTRODUCTION

Rehabilitation programs target the specific needs of inmates in an effort to lower the number of repeat offenders. These programs provide a range of assistance, including educational possibilities, leisure pursuits, job training, and family visitor opportunities. Collaboration between social workers, community organizations, and prison officials is crucial for the success of these initiatives. By providing comprehensive assistance and addressing the underlying factors that lead to criminal activity, these programs seek to interrupt the cycle of reoffending and improve outcomes for both people and society.

The proper implementation of restorative justice is severely hampered by the appalling circumstances in Philippine prisons. The fundamental tenets of justice that these institutions seek to preserve are undermined when they continue a cycle of violence, neglect, and overcrowding instead of rehabilitating and reintegrating criminals into society. Despite the police's authority, which is represented by their uniforms and badges, PDLs often find themselves engaged in an ongoing struggle for control inside these establishments. They engage in a delicate dance of resistance, arguing and bargaining their position inside a system that is biased against them, in order to confront the system's basic structural defects. These dynamics draw attention to the pervasive problems that need to be addressed in order to promote rehabilitation and a real sense of justice in the Philippine penal system (Nario-Lopez, 2021).

Deprivation of liberty is a way for the state to prevent crime and keep peace within society. When someone disrupts that peace, it's important to have a fair and transparent legal system in place. For this system to work well, the different parts of the government and its processes need to work together smoothly and efficiently to ensure justice is served (Manzano et al. 2021).

Enhancing the professional standards and skills of the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) and Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) is the main goal of Republic Act No. 9263, commonly known as the BFP and BJMP Professionalization Act of 2004. By requiring that correctional officials have proper training, facilities, and resources, the Act indirectly promotes rehabilitation programs even if its primary goals are the professionalization of staff and the enhancement of service delivery. By focusing on their wellbeing and possible reintegration into society, this guarantees a compassionate and therapeutic setting for PDLs. The Act emphasizes how prison management procedures, including the establishment of successful rehabilitation programs for PDLs, must be continuously improved.

Based on the context above, the researcher aims to explore how well rehabilitation programs are being implemented at the North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories, and what challenges are being faced. The study will also look into whether there are differences in how these programs are carried out based on factors like the demographic profile of the individuals involved. Finally, it will examine whether there's a connection between the effectiveness of the programs and the issues encountered during their implementation.

Research Questions

The purpose of this research was to determine the degree of rehabilitation program implementation for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) and the scope of issues that arose during the program's execution.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the PDLs in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sex;
 - 1.2. Age;
 - 1.3. Civil Status; and,
 - 1.4. Types of Offense?
2. What is the implementation level of the rehabilitation programs for PDLs in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. Educational Program;
 - 2.2. Livelihood Program; and,
 - 2.3. Recreational Program?
3. What is the extent of the problems encountered in the implementation of rehabilitation programs for PDL?
4. Is there a significant difference in the implementation level of rehabilitation programs for PDL when grouped according to demographic profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the implementation level and the extent of problems encountered on the rehabilitation programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty?

Hypotheses

All tests were tested at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the implementation level of rehabilitation programs for Persons Deprived with Liberty when grouped according to demographic profile.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between the implementation level and the extent of the problems encountered on the rehabilitation programs.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In order to investigate the correlations between variables, this study used a quantitative research strategy, which is centered on collecting and evaluating numerical data. The study's main goal was to ascertain if the degree of rehabilitation program implementation and the severity of issues faced by PDLs in the male and female dormitories of the North Cotabato District Jail are significantly correlated.

Specifically, this study employed a descriptive-correlation approach to analyze both the demographic characteristics of the respondents and the potential relationship

between the implementation level of rehabilitation programs and the extent of problems encountered. The descriptive aspect involved summarizing the demographic profile of the PDLs to provide a detailed account of the respondents' profiles. Meanwhile, the correlational method was used to identify the relationship between the effectiveness of rehabilitation programs and the challenges faced, aiming to determine if significant relationship exist between these two variables.

Research Locale

This research was conducted in the North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories in Amas, Kidapawan City, in the province of Cotabato. The facility is situated in Barangay Amas, Kidapawan City, close to the governor's office. Kidapawan's roots lie in the same-named municipal area, which was first occupied by the Monuvu people and created by the Americans in 1914. Tribal chieftain Datu Siawan Ingal was named District President. Ilonggo settlers gradually moved into the region.

Located in the Soccsksargen area of Mindanao, Cotabato, sometimes referred to as North Cotabato, is a landlocked province in the Philippines. Its capital is Kidapawan City. Some of its municipalities are under the jurisdiction of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region, which is nearby. Today, North Cotabato is a prosperous and culturally diverse province, renowned for its breathtaking landscapes, booming agricultural sector, and rich cultural heritage. Initiatives to promote peace, sustainable development, and cultural diversity are shaping the province's history and future despite enduring challenges.

North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories serve larger cities and municipalities and house PDLs awaiting trial or serving 1–3-year sentences; city jails house PDLs sentenced to 1-3 years; and municipal jails house those sentenced to under 6 months.

Respondents

A total of two hundred two (202) Persons Deprived of Liberty, twenty-five (25) from North Cotabato Female Dormitory and one hundred seventy-seven (177) from North Cotabato Male Dormitory. This study employed total enumeration. It is used in research within a jail setting because the population size is often manageable, and including every individual ensures a comprehensive and accurate understanding of the context. This approach eliminates sampling bias and provides a holistic view of the demographic, behavioral, and experiential data of the PDLs. It is particularly effective in jails, where each PDLs circumstances contribute significantly to evaluating programs, policies, and systemic issues, making the findings more robust and representative of the entire facility population. Total PDLs inside the jail were included except with contagious diseases and those belonging to high-risk prison populations are excluded.

Research Instruments

Data on the execution of rehabilitation programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in the North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories was gathered via

a survey questionnaire. The objective was to evaluate these initiatives' efficacy and pinpoint any issues that arose. Based on the PDLs' demographic characteristics, the research also sought to ascertain if there were any notable variations in the way the rehabilitation programs were implemented.

The purpose of the questionnaire was to assess the degree of implementation and the difficulties PDLs encountered in these dorms. In order to get quantitative data, Leonor (2023) changed and updated an earlier questionnaire.

Two components comprised the modified and adapted questionnaire. Data on the PDLs' demographics and the kind of crime they committed were collected in the first part. The evaluation of rehabilitation programs in the North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories was the main objective of the second segment. It examined livelihood, recreational, and educational initiatives as well as the difficulties in implementing them. In this research, answers were measured using a 5-point Likert scale:

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.50-5.00	Strongly Agree	Indicates a very high agreement with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs
3.50-4.49	Agree	This signifies a high agreement with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs but not as strong as “strongly agree.”
2.50-3.49	Moderate Agree	This signifies a moderate level of agreement with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs.
1.50-2.49	Disagree	Signifies less disagreement with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs, but not as strong as “strongly disagree.”
1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree	Indicates the least disagreement with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs

The third part of the instrument elicits questions about the problems encountered in the implementation of community involvement in the rehabilitation of PDL. A 5-Point Likert-Scale was used in this study:

Mean Range	Description	Interpretation
4.50-5.00	Very Satisfied	Indicates the least extent of problems encountered with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs
3.50-4.49	Satisfied	Signifies less extent of problems encountered with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs, but not as strong as “strongly dissatisfaction.”
2.50-3.49	Moderately Satisfied	This signifies a moderate level of extent of problems encountered with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs.
1.50-2.49	Dissatisfied	This signifies a high extent of problems encountered with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs but not as strong as “very satisfied.”
1.00-1.49	Very Dissatisfied	Indicates a very high extent of problems encountered with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs

Data Gathering Procedure

The study underwent ethical clearance to ensure adherence to ethical standards, minimize harm to participants, and achieve beneficial outcomes. Following this, the researcher prepared an authorization letter addressed to the Regional Director JCSUPT Leo P Baldon of Region XII Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) to seek permission to conduct the study in the North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories, which was approved. Subsequently, a request letter was submitted to JCINSP Teddy G Uchi for NCDJ Male Dormitory and to JSINSP Eunice Cobacha for

NCDJ Female Dormitory to gain permission for the study. Once these approvals were secured, the researcher, with the assistance of dormitory personnel, distributed permission letters to Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) to obtain their informed consent for participation.

For the data collection, the researcher personally explained the purpose of the study, the instructions for completing the questionnaire, and emphasized the voluntary nature of participation, assuring respondents that they could decline without any negative consequences. To protect respondents' identities, pseudonyms were used when reporting findings, and strict confidentiality measures were implemented. Respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, which was subsequently collected by BJMP personnel to ensure the researcher's safety.

After all the data were collected, the researcher organized and tallied the gathered responses, then subjected the data to statistical analysis at a significant level of 0.05. The results were subsequently interpreted using appropriate statistical techniques to derive meaningful conclusions and insights.

Data Analysis

Every piece of data was examined at the significance level of 0.5. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test was used to determine if the data was normal.

Frequency and percentage were used in order to ascertain the demographic characteristics of the PDLs. Both frequency and weighted mean were utilized to evaluate the degree of rehabilitation program implementation in the North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories. The same techniques were used to assess the degree of issues that arose throughout the execution of these initiatives.

The Mann-Whitney U Test was used for sex, and the Kruskal-Wallis Test was used for age, civil status, and type of offense in order to ascertain whether there were any notable variations in the way rehabilitation programs were implemented depending on these variables. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test indicated that the data was not regularly distributed, which is why these tests were used.

Finally, since the data also did not follow normal distribution, the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient was employed to evaluate the association between the implementation level and the severity of issues observed in the rehabilitation programs.

RESULTS

Demographic Profile of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)

Shown in Table 1 are the results of a survey of demographic profile of PDLs conducted.

The table below presents the distribution of participants by sex, highlighting the frequency and percentage of males and females in the study:

Table 1
Demographic Profile of the PDLs in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	177	87.62%
Female	25	12.38%
TOTAL	202	100%

Table 1 provides a comprehensive breakdown of the demographic profile of the 202 PDLs in North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories, focusing specifically on their sex. Among the total respondents, a significant majority of 177 individuals, representing 87.62%, are male. In contrast, 25 respondents, or 12.38%, were female. This data underscores the predominance of male PDLs in the facility, highlighting a notable gender disparity within the PDLs population. The findings suggest that men were more likely to be incarcerated in this particular institution compared to women, reflecting broader trends observed in correctional systems.

The Vera Institute of Justice reported that in 2019, the total number of people incarcerated in state and federal prisons in the U.S. was 1,435,500, with the overwhelming majority being men. This aligns with broader trends indicating that men are significantly more likely to be imprisoned than women (Fugere, 2023).

As shown in Table 2 a breakdown of PDLs by age group, detailing the frequency and percentage of individuals in each category. This data provides an overview of the age distribution within the sample population.

Table 2
Demographic Profile of the PDLs in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
67 and above	2	0.99%
60- 66 years old	3	1.49%
53- 59 years old	10	4.95%
46- 52 years old	26	12.87%
39- 45 years old	36	17.82%
32- 38 years old	53	26.24%
25- 31 years old	52	25.74%
18- 24 years old	20	9.90%
TOTAL	202	100%

As shown in Table 2, a detailed distribution of the age ranges among the 202 PDLs in North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories. The data revealed a varied

age profile, with a notable concentration of individuals in certain age brackets. Specifically, 9.90% of the PDLs were between the ages of 18 and 24, indicating that a smaller portion of the population is comprised of young adults. A larger proportion, 25.74%, falls within the 25 to 31 age range, suggested that a significant number of individuals are in their early adulthood.

The largest age group, comprising 26.24% of the PDLs, was between 32 and 38 years old, highlighting that most of the PDLs were in their mid-to-late thirties. Following this, 17.82% were aged 39 to 45, indicating a moderate representation of middle-aged individuals. As the age brackets increase, the numbers steadily decline, with 12.87% of PDLs aged 46 to 52, 4.95% aged 53 to 59, and a smaller proportion of 1.49% between 60 and 66 years old. Only 0.99% of the PDLs are 67 years old or above, reflecting a very small elderly population within the facility.

This age distribution suggests that the majority of PDLs are in their prime working years (32-38 years old), followed closely by those in their early to mid-adulthood (25-31 years old). The decreasing numbers in the older age brackets could indicate either a lower incarceration rate among older individuals or earlier release due to factors such as health or parole eligibility. Overall, the data demonstrates a concentration of PDLs in their mid-thirties, which could have implications for rehabilitation programs and other services provided in the facility, as they are likely to cater to individuals in this age group.

The table below presents the distribution of respondents based on their civil status, showing the frequency and percentage for each category.

Table 3

Demographic Profile of the PDLs in terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	109	53.96%
Married	88	43.56%
Widow	5	2.48%
TOTAL	202	100%

Table 3 provides an in-depth analysis of the demographic profile of the 202 PDLs in North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories, with a specific focus on their civil status. The data reveals distinct categories of civil status, offering valuable insight into the personal backgrounds of the incarcerated individuals.

A majority of the PDLs, 53.96%, are single, accounting for over half of the population. This indicates that a significant portion of the PDLs is not married or in formal partnerships. This finding may suggest a correlation between single status and factors that lead to incarceration, such as a lack of family support systems, economic instability, or higher levels of risk-taking behavior commonly associated with individuals without familial responsibilities.

Meanwhile, 43.56% of the PDLs were married, representing a substantial portion of the population who were in committed relationships or have family obligations. This group may face additional challenges during their incarceration, including concerns over their roles as breadwinners or caregivers, which could influence their psychological well-being and participation in rehabilitation programs.

A smaller percentage of the PDLs, 2.48%, were widows representing a very minor portion of the population. This category reflected individuals who had lost their spouses, which may introduce unique emotional and social vulnerability, such as isolation or grief, during their time in detention.

The data on civil status within North Cotabato District Jail revealed a striking difference in the personal lives of those incarcerated, offering a glimpse into how relationship dynamics may shape their experiences both inside and outside of the facility. The predominance of single PDLs, who made up more than half of the PDLs population, suggests that many of these individuals may lack the emotional and social anchor that a family or partner can provide. Without the stabilizing influence of a committed relationship, single PDLs might be more vulnerable to feelings of isolation, emotional distress, or difficulty envisioning a structured life post-incarceration. The absence of a familial support system could hinder their ability to find direction and purpose, making their rehabilitation and eventual reintegration into society a more complex process. Programs that focus on building social connections, fostering self-reliance, and encouraging the development of personal goals may be particularly beneficial for this group.

On the other hand, the significant proportion of married PDLs indicated that a considerable number of PDLs do have strong family ties. For those individuals, their incarceration may involve not just personal consequences but also profound impacts on their spouses, children, and dependents. However, having a family may also serve as a source of hope and motivation, with the promise of reunion and rebuilding family life providing a powerful incentive for good behavior and engagement in rehabilitation efforts. Those PDLs might benefit from programs that facilitate communication with their families, helping them maintain relationships that could be pivotal in their post-incarceration journey.

Understanding the distinct challenges faced by both single and married PDLs were essential in designing effective rehabilitation programs. Single PDLs often struggle with the absence of a strong personal support network, which can make it harder to build emotional stability and a sense of belonging. Rehabilitation efforts for them should focus on fostering self-growth through mentorship, peer support, and therapy to develop personal resilience. In contrast, married PDLs face the additional challenge of maintaining or rebuilding family relationships, which can be a crucial factor in their successful reintegration. For this group, rehabilitation should include family counseling, parenting programs, and support structures that help them plan for a smoother transition back into family life. By addressing the unique emotional and practical needs of each group, rehabilitation programs can more effectively support the reintegration process,

acknowledging that personal relationships, whether individual or familial, play a pivotal role in shaping their path toward reintegration and societal acceptance.

As shown in Table 4, the summary of various types of offenses, detailing their frequency and corresponding percentage distributions. It highlights the prevalence of certain crime categories over others within the recorded data set.

Table 4

Demographic Profile of the PDLs in terms of Types of Offense

Types of Offense	Frequency	Percentage
Crimes Against Public Interest	2	0.99%
Crimes Against Person	73	36.14%
Crimes Against Property	11	5.45%
Special Laws	105	51.98%
Crimes Against Public Officers	1	0.50%
Crimes Against Fundamental Laws of the State	1	0.50%
Crimes Against Public Morals	1	0.50%
Crimes Against Chastity	1	0.50%
Crimes Committed by Public Officer	1	0.50%
Crimes Against National Security and the Law of Nations	0	0
Crimes Against Personal Liberty and Security	0	0
Crimes Against Honor	0	0
TOTAL	202	100%

Table 1.4 presents the data that the most frequently committed offenses are those under Special Laws, accounting for 105 cases or 51.98%, indicating a significant prevalence of violations related to specific statutory regulations. This is followed by Crimes Against Person, with 73 cases or 36.14%, highlighting the notable occurrence of offenses involving physical harm or threats to individuals. On the other hand, the least frequent offenses, each with only 1 case or 0.50%, include Crimes Against Public Officers, Crimes Against Fundamental Laws of the State, Crimes Against Public Morals, Crimes Against Chastity, and Crimes Committed by Public Officer, suggesting that these offenses are relatively rare within the studied population. Additionally, no cases were recorded for Crimes Against National Security and the Law of Nations, Crimes Against Personal Liberty and Security, or Crimes Against Honor, reflecting their absence in this dataset.

These findings suggest a concentration of offenses in areas governed by special laws and interpersonal conflicts, reflecting specific enforcement and societal challenges in addressing these issues.

The Implementation Level of Rehabilitation Programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)

Rehabilitation programs for PDLs are essential for supporting their reintegration into society. These programs aim to meet various needs, such as education, livelihood, and recreational.

Shown in Table 2.1 highlights the results of survey about aforementioned subject.

The table below presents the evaluation of the educational program offered by the BJMP based on selected indicators.

Table 5

Implementation Level of the Rehabilitation Programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in terms of Educational Programs

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. I learned so much from the educational program of the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP).	4.37	High
2. The knowledge that I have gained gives me additional self-esteem.	4.30	High
3. Through the educational program of the BJMP, I become more confident to relate to people.	4.36	High
4. The educational program of the BJMP is very effective in preparing the PDLs to face a life outside of prison.	4.30	High
5. The BJMP is employing competent teachers or instructors for our educational development.	4.50	Very High
Total Mean	4.37	High

Table 5 highlighted the effectiveness of educational programs for PDLs at North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories, with PDLs expressed high satisfaction with their teachers, reflected in a weighted mean of 4.50 indicating Very High. This suggests that competent instructors provide essential knowledge and a sense of purpose during incarceration. However, areas like the boost in self-esteem from education and the program's effectiveness in preparing PDLs for life after prison scored slightly lower at 4.30 which also means High. While PDLs value those programs, they may still face challenges related to self-confidence and uncertainty about how their new skills will translate to opportunities post-release.

The overall weighted mean of 4.37 is interpreted as high which signifies a high implementation in terms of the educational programs. This suggests that the BJMP have

high levels of implementation of their educational programs for the PDLs in North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories. It signifies a high agreement with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs. The influenced-on self-esteem and post-release preparedness, however, indicated places for growth even while PDLs exhibit trust in the instructional material. This emphasizes the necessity of improving educational programs' practical applicability in addition to their quality to give PDLs the confidence they need to confidently reintegrate into society. All things considered; the unanimous agreement provides a solid basis for the advancement of rehabilitation programs in the future.

This finding was corroborated by research from He (2024), this study consistently underscored the important role of access to education within the prison system for successful reintegration.

The table below presents an evaluation of the livelihood programs based on key indicators and their corresponding mean scores.

Table 6

Implementation Level of the Rehabilitation Programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in terms of Livelihood Programs

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. The Bureau of Jail Management and Penology (BJMP) offers a variety of livelihood programs for the PDL.	4.14	High
2. Through the livelihood programs, we learn a lot that can prepare us when we go out of prison.	4.19	High
3. The livelihood programs make our time worthwhile.	4.01	High
4. We are able to earn while in prison.	3.69	High
5. We are able to provide for our family's needs even we are in prison.	3.54	High
Total Mean	3.91	High

Table 6 showed that the livelihood programs for PDLs at North Cotabato District Jail were generally well-received, with an overall weighted mean of 3.91, indicating High agreement on their effectiveness. The programs were particularly valued for teaching skills that can help PDLs prepare for life after prison, as reflected in the highest score of 4.19 which means High. However, PDLs expressed slightly lower satisfaction 3.54 but also means High with their ability to support their families while still incarcerated. Overall, the livelihood programs were seen as beneficial, but there were challenges in meeting immediate family needs while in jail.

Not all PDLs are able to support their families financially while incarcerated, as many face limitations despite their best efforts. Some PDLs, especially these with specific

skills or a strong willingness to learn, can take advantage of livelihood programs offered in jail to earn a modest income. These individuals may be able to send money to their families, helping to ease the financial strain of their absence. However, for others, earning while in jail remains a challenge. Factors such as lack of prior skills, limited opportunities within the facility, or personal circumstances prevent them from generating income. This disparity highlights the need for more inclusive and accessible livelihood opportunities, ensuring that all PDLs, regardless of background or ability, had a chance to contribute to their families' well-being.

The study by Inusa (2021) highlighted the transformative impact of livelihood skills on the rehabilitation of PDLs, showing that through Livelihood Training Programs, individuals not only learn practical skills that enhanced their job prospects upon release but also undergo significant personal growth. These programs instill a sense of purpose and self-worth in PDLs, which is essential for reintegration into society. By participating in skill-building activities, they developed discipline, responsibility, and a work ethic, fostering a positive mindset that helps counteract the negative influences of prison life. Importantly, the study suggested that those skills can significantly reduce recidivism rates by providing PDLs with legitimate avenues to earn a living, addressing the economic hardships that often contribute to criminal behavior. PDLs who leave prison with marketable skills were better equipped to find stable employment, which not only supports their own development but also positively impacts their families and communities. Ultimately, Inusa's research emphasized that vocational training is more than just a means to employment; it is a crucial element of effective rehabilitation that can lead to meaningful change in PDLs' lives, benefiting society.

The table below presents the indicators, and corresponding mean scores related to recreational activities.

Table 7

Implementation Level of the Rehabilitation Programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in terms of Recreational Programs

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. We are given enough time for recreational activities.	4.08	High
2. Sports and exercise keep us strong and healthy.	4.12	High
3. We have enough sports facilities and equipment.	3.99	High
4. We are also given time to celebrate during special occasions.	4.11	High
5. The sports and recreational activities enable us to develop the spirit of camaraderie and friendship.	4.11	High
Total Mean	4.08	High

Table 7 revealed that the recreational programs for PDLs at North Cotabato District Jail were highly valued, with an overall weighted mean of 4.08 which means High, indicating a strong level of agreement regarding their implementation. The highest mean score of 4.12 which means High highlights the positive impact of sports and exercise on PDLs' physical health and well-being, underscoring their importance in maintaining strength and fitness during incarceration. However, the lowest mean of 3.99—still interpreted as High suggested that while those programs were well-received, there may be areas for improvement or greater engagement. Overall, the data indicated that recreational programs were effectively implemented within the facility, contributing significantly to the PDLs' rehabilitation and promoting a healthier lifestyle.

The findings about the recreational programs at North Cotabato District Jail imply that these initiatives play a crucial role in supporting the physical health and overall well-being of PDLs. Engaging in sports and exercise not only helps PDLs maintain their strength and fitness but also offers a valuable outlet for stress relief and camaraderie among peers. However, the slight room for improvement suggests that there is an opportunity to enhance participation and engagement in these programs, which could further enrich the rehabilitation experience. By continuing to prioritize and expand recreational activities, the facility can foster a more supportive environment that encourages PDLs to stay active, build positive relationships, and develop healthy habits that were essential for their reintegration into society.

According to Ortega et al. (2020), when properly oriented, sport can aid in a person's overall formation because as PDLs taking part in sports programs themselves acknowledge, they not only learn technical-sporting aspects, but also personal and social values that facilitate their future integration into society. In addition, specialist literature emphasizes the need for such programs to be carried out in partnership with sports organizations and clubs from outside the prison. Moreover, it is important to explore PDLs' perceptions of sports programs, in order to assess their potential and impact.

The table below presents the mean scores for various community programs, including educational, livelihood, and recreational initiatives.

Table 8

Summary Table on the Implementation Level of Rehabilitation Programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty

Sub-variables	Mean	Description
Educational Programs	4.37	High
Livelihood Programs	3.91	High
Recreational Programs	4.08	High
Overall Mean	4.12	High

The data revealed that educational programs for PDLs were the most effectively implemented rehabilitation initiatives, receiving strong positive feedback from PDLs who appreciated the opportunities for learning and personal growth with a mean of 4.37 which

means High. While livelihood programs scored lower in implementation with a mean of 3.91 but still means High, they still garnered favorable responses, indicated that PDLs recognized their value despite being less prioritized. This suggested a critical need to bolster the focus on livelihood programs, ensuring that they were not overshadowed by educational efforts. By enhancing these programs, correctional facilities can better equip PDLs with practical skills for future employment, complementing the strong educational foundation and ultimately improving their chances of successful reintegration into society.

The overall mean of 4.12, which means High for the rehabilitation programs indicates a strong positive perception among PDLs regarding the effectiveness of the programs in place. This high level of agreement suggests that PDLs found value in the combined educational, livelihood, and recreational initiatives, viewing them as beneficial to their rehabilitation and personal development. It implies that the programs are well-implemented and contributed significantly to the PDLs' overall well-being and preparedness for reintegration into society. However, it also highlighted the importance of maintaining and enhancing these programs, particularly focusing on areas that may need improvement, such as livelihood opportunities, to ensure that all aspects of rehabilitation are effectively addressed and that PDLs were fully supported in their journeys toward successful reintegration.

According to the study of Arbour et al. (2021) it suggested that, in certain circumstances, incarceration could play a role in aiding offenders' social reintegration. However, the mechanisms through which imprisonment facilitates successful recovery remain largely unclear. The study emphasizes that for rehabilitation programs to effectively reduce recidivism, it is crucial that PDLs were assessed through methods that accurately identify their criminogenic needs, those factors that contribute to criminal behavior. Without such assessments, the potential for rehabilitation may be diminished, as programs may fail to address the specific factors that drive an individual's criminal behavior. This underscores the importance of a tailored, individualized approach to rehabilitation that takes into account the unique circumstances and challenges each offender faces, as well as the need for continuous evaluation and adaptation of rehabilitation strategies to ensure their effectiveness in promoting long-term social reintegration.

This table presents the extent of problems related to the rehabilitation programs and overall experience of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs).

Table 9

Extent of the Problems Encountered in the Implementation of Rehabilitation Programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. Availability of funds in implementing effective rehabilitation programs for PDL.	4.05	Less

2. The number of jails personnels may affect the quality of services provided to PDL.	3.91	Less
4. Issuance of bedtime essentials and other personal belongings.	3.92	Less
5. The experience of PDLs in treatment of medical conditions.	3.97	Less
6. The jail imposes rules on who can visit and limits the number of visitors allowed per visit.	3.92	Less
7. Availability of materials for educational purposes like books, magazines and computers.	3.85	Less
8. Time given for recreational activities to engage in leisure pursuits.	3.88	Less
9. Applying in a job after serving sentence.	4.08	Less
10. The experience of PDL in receiving visitors.	4.07	Less
Total Mean	3.97	Less

Table 9 shows the total mean of 3.97 which indicates less extent of problems encountered among the PDLs. The highest mean score 4.08 was observed in the item application of job after serving sentence highlighting the significance of employment opportunities for PDLs post-incarceration. It suggests that these issues are becoming less pervasive or severe due to societal changes, legal reforms, or supportive programs. Similarly, the experience of PDLs in receiving visitors 4.07 ranked as the second highest, suggests that compared to other issues they face, PDLs generally have fewer difficulties when it comes to receiving visitors. On the other hand, the lowest mean score 3.85 was observed in the availability of materials for educational purposes, such as books, magazines, and computers. This suggests that the correctional facilities are struggling to provide sufficient educational tools and materials, which are essential for promoting personal development, literacy, and vocational skills. The lack of up-to-date books, limited access to diverse reading materials, and inadequate computer resources could hinder PDLs' ability to engage in meaningful educational activities, limiting their potential for rehabilitation and reintegration into society. Such shortcomings may stem from budget constraints, overcrowding, or the under-prioritization of educational programs within the facility, ultimately impacting the overall effectiveness of rehabilitation efforts.

The less extent of problems encountered with the implementation level of rehabilitation programs, the challenges or issues faced during the execution of rehabilitation programs are relatively minimal. In other words, the programs are being implemented with fewer difficulties, and the intended goals are being achieved with less disruption or barriers. This suggests that, in most areas, the rehabilitation programs are functioning well, with PDLs generally experiencing fewer obstacles in accessing or participating in these programs. However, as highlighted by the lower score for educational materials, some specific areas—like resource availability—still pose notable challenges, indicating that while the programs are working to some extent, improvements are needed in certain aspects for optimal success.

This experience dispels myths about how easy it was to live in jail and urges young people to stay out of trouble. Such encounters build a greater understanding and empathy for the difficulties experienced behind jail walls by providing insightful information about the reality of incarceration (Cerbania & Magbojos, 2024).

The following table presents the results of a Mann-Whitney U test conducted to compare the mean scores between male and female participants. The test evaluates whether there is a significant difference in the distribution of scores based on sex. The p-value indicates whether the difference observed is statistically significant.

Table 10

Significant Difference in the Implementation Level of Rehabilitation Programs for PDL when Grouped According to Sex

Sex	Mean	U-value (Mann-Whitney U Test)	p-value	Remarks
Male	4.06	1452.50	0.00	Significant
Female	4.57			

As shown in Table 10 the results indicated a statistically significant difference in the implementation level of rehabilitation programs for PDL when grouped according to sex. Females had a higher mean score, 4.57 compared to males, 4.06 suggesting that females rated the measured variable. The *U-value* (1452.50) in the Mann-Whitney U Test represents the statistic used to compare the ranks of scores between two independent groups—in this case, males and females. It is calculated by assessing the distribution and ranks of the scores within both groups. A higher U-value indicates more significant differences in ranks between the two groups. The *p-value* (0.00) shows us the probability that the observed difference between the two groups occurred by chance. A p-value of 0.00 indicates a very low likelihood that the difference is random, suggesting that the difference between the male and female groups is statistically significant. Since the p-value is less than the typical significance threshold of 0.05, it confirms that the mean scores of males (4.06) and females (4.57) are significantly different from each other.

This suggests that female PDLs may perceive the programs more positively. This could indicate that the programs are more effectively tailored to meet the needs of females or that female participants experience better engagement and outcomes. Studies have shown that gender differences in prison rehabilitation programs are influenced by factors such as social support systems, program accessibility, and gender-specific needs. Therefore, this finding highlights the importance of considering gender when designing and evaluating rehabilitation initiatives to enhance their effectiveness.

This review highlights a gap in global knowledge about the relationship between sex and/or gender and rehabilitation participation and outcomes within health systems.

Future research should rely on social science and intersectional approaches to elucidate how gender and other social norms, roles, and structures influence a gender disparity in rehabilitation participation and outcomes. Health systems should prioritize person-centered, gender-responsive care, which involves delivering services that are responsive to the complex social norms, roles, and structures that intersect to shape gender inequitable rehabilitation participation and outcomes in diverse contexts (Ott et al., 2022).

The following table presents the mean scores of different age groups, along with the results of the Kruskal-Wallis test to assess the significance of age differences. The H-value and p-value are provided to evaluate whether age has a statistically significant impact on the observed scores across the groups.

Table 11

Significant Difference in the Implementation Level of Rehabilitation Programs for PDL When Grouped According to Age

Age	Mean	H-Value (Kruskal-Wallis Test)	p-value	Remarks
67 and above	4.43	13.25	0.07	Not Significant
60- 66 years old	4.76			
53- 59 years old	4.72			
46- 52 years old	4.32			
39- 45 years old	4.03			
32- 38 years old	4.11			
25- 31 years old	3.91			
18- 24 years old	4.17			

Table 11 showed the *H-value* of 13.25, derived from the Kruskal-Wallis Test, which is used to assess whether there are significant differences in the mean scores across the different age groups. The Kruskal-Wallis Test is a non-parametric method that compares the ranks of data from multiple groups—in this case, different age categories. A higher H-value suggests a greater difference in ranks between the age groups. The *p-value* of 0.07 indicates that the observed differences in mean scores across the various age groups are not statistically significant at the commonly used significance level of 0.05. Since the *p-value* is greater than 0.05, the result is considered not significant, meaning that, based on this data, there is insufficient evidence to suggest that age has a meaningful impact on the scores. Therefore, while there may be differences in the mean scores for different age groups, these differences are likely due to chance rather than any actual effect of age.

However, the observed trend where older age groups (53 and above) tend to rate the programs more positively could indicate that older individuals may perceive or

experience rehabilitation efforts more favorably. This trend could reflect greater life experience, which might lead to more favorable evaluations of rehabilitation programs, as older individuals may have a deeper understanding of their needs and the benefits of such interventions.

A study published in BMC Health Services Research explored rehabilitation program delivery for older adults, finding that older age groups often benefit from more tailored, person-centered approaches that focus on functional improvement. This supports the trend of higher perceived program effectiveness in older individuals. The study revealed that rehabilitation services, especially for those aged 50 and above, often emphasize psychological interventions, therapeutic exercises, and self-management education, all of which contribute to more positive outcomes in older age groups (Geohagen, 2022).

The table below presents the results of the Kruskal-Wallis test, which was conducted to analyze the differences in means based on civil status. The p-value and H-value are provided to assess the significance of the results for each civil status group.

Table 12

Significant Difference in the Implementation Level of Rehabilitation Programs for PDL when Grouped According to Civil Status

Civil Status	Mean	H-Value (Kruskal-Wallis Test)	p-value	Remarks
Single	4.07	0.745	0.69	Not Significant
Married	4.17			
Widow	4.36			

Table 12 shows the *H-value* of 0.745, derived from the Kruskal-Wallis Test, reflects the statistical comparison of the mean scores across different civil status groups (Single, Married, Widow). The Kruskal-Wallis Test ranks the data within these groups to determine if there are any significant differences. The *p-value* of 0.69 indicates that the differences in mean scores between the civil status categories are not statistically significant, as it is much higher than the commonly used threshold of 0.05. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the result is considered not significant, meaning there is no strong evidence to suggest that civil status (whether single, married, or widowed) has a meaningful impact on the variable being measured. Thus, any observed differences in the mean scores across these groups are likely due to random variation rather than a real effect.

The findings suggest that while civil status does not significantly impact the level of satisfaction with rehabilitation programs for PDLs, there is a slight trend indicating that widowed PDLs may perceive these programs more positively. This could be due to their emotional or social needs, which may be differently addressed by the programs.

However, the lack of statistical significance implies that these differences are not strong enough to draw broad conclusions, suggesting that factors beyond civil status may be more influential in shaping perceptions of rehabilitation effectiveness.

The lack of a statistically significant difference in the implementation level of rehabilitation programs based on civil status in your study aligns with findings from related research. Several studies have examined the satisfaction and effectiveness of rehabilitation programs in jails, particularly the role of civil status in shaping the experiences of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs). For instance, a study conducted in the Ilocos Sur Provincial Jail found that while civil status had some relationship with the level of satisfaction among inmates, it was not always a dominant factor. Specifically, married individuals were shown to report higher levels of satisfaction, particularly in moral and social aspects of rehabilitation programs. This aligns with broader research suggesting that marital status and social support systems, such as family connections, significantly influence the reintegration success and well-being of inmates (de Vera et al, 2022).

The following table presents the results of a Kruskal-Wallis test on various types of offenses, along with their corresponding mean values, H-values, and p-values. The p-value helps determine the statistical significance of differences between the groups, with remarks indicating whether the differences are significant or not.

Table 13
Significant Difference in the Implementation Level of Rehabilitation Programs for PDL when Grouped According to Types of Offense

Types of Offense	Mean	H-Value (Kruskal-Wallis Test)	p-value	Remarks
Crimes Against Public Interest	3.50			
Crimes Against Person	4.06			
Crimes Against Property	4.41			
Special Laws	4.10			
Crimes Against Public Order	4.61			
Crimes Against Public Officer	5.00	9.7792	0.37	Not Significant
Crimes Against Fundamental Laws of State	4.27			
Crimes Against Public Morals	4.93			
Crime Against Chastity	3.93			
Crimes Committed by Public Officer	4.93			

As shown in Table 13, there was no statistically significant difference in the mean scores across the different types of offenses. While not significant, the mean scores suggested variations in responses, with offenses like Crimes Against Public Officers and Crimes Committed by Public Officers having higher ratings compared to others, potentially reflecting differences in how individuals associated with those offenses perceive or experience the measured variable. The *H-value* (9.7792) corresponds to the comparison of the different types of offenses and their mean scores. It is derived from the Kruskal-Wallis Test, which is a rank-based test often used when the data doesn't meet the assumptions required for an ANOVA (like normality or equal variances). The *p-value* of 0.37 indicates that the differences in mean scores across the types of offenses are not significant. This means that the variation in scores observed between the different categories of offenses (e.g., Crimes Against Public Officer, Crimes Against Property, etc.) is likely due to chance, and there's no strong evidence to suggest that these groups differ meaningfully in terms of the specific issues being measured (e.g., implementation of rehabilitation programs).

The lack of a statistically significant difference in mean scores across different types of offenses suggests that while the offenses themselves may not influence perceptions uniformly, certain offenses like Crimes Against Public Officers and Crimes Committed by Public Officers receive higher ratings. This could imply that individuals involved in these types of offenses may perceive rehabilitation programs or the legal system differently, possibly due to the social and institutional stigma associated with these crimes.

The study analyzed public and PDLs' opinions, revealing that individuals convicted of certain offenses, such as crimes against public officers or violent crimes, tend to have different perspectives on rehabilitation programs compared to others. Although the differences in responses were not statistically significant, variations in perceptions may reflect underlying biases or experiences, particularly with regard to how those offenses are treated in the rehabilitation process (Mehta et al., 2020).

The following table presents a summary of the findings regarding the level of implementation and the extent of problems encountered. The results provide insights into the effectiveness and challenges faced during the implementation process.

Table 14

Significant Relationship Between the Implementation Level and the Extent of Problems Encountered of Rehabilitation Programs for PDL

Variables	Mean	r_s	p-value	Remarks
Level of Implementation	4.12	-0.82	0.00	Significant
Extent of Problems Encountered	3.97			

The result in Table 14 showed that there was a statistically significant negative correlation between the level of implementation and the extent of problems encountered with the r_s value of 0.82 and the p value of 0.00 which is less than the significance level of 0.05 . This suggests that as the level of implementation increases, the extent of problems tends to decrease.

This result is in line with the study of Kiani et al. (2020), revealed that statistically significant negative correlation between the level of implementation and the extent of operational problems. As organizations adopted practices more thoroughly, the frequency and severity of operational issues, such as inefficiencies and delays, were reduced.

This suggests that more thorough and systematic implementation can effectively address challenges such as logistical issues, resource limitations, and operational inefficiencies. Improved planning, better allocation of resources, and a more structured approach may help in minimizing these problems, leading to smoother execution and better outcomes.

Welch's (1996) rehabilitation theory underscores the significance of using structured programs and strategies that not only rehabilitate individuals but also promote their successful reintegration into society. The theory aligns with the study's findings, which highlight the extensive implementation of rehabilitation programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) and the strong correlation between these programs and the challenges faced by PDLs. According to Welch, the experiences within correctional environments are pivotal in shaping an individual's transformation, emphasizing that the process of rehabilitation is not just about changing behavior but also about fostering a deeper, more meaningful transformation of identity. This broader approach recognizes that effective rehabilitation requires more than just addressing criminal behavior—it involves providing the support, guidance, and opportunities necessary for individuals to rebuild their lives and prepare for a successful return to society. The theory, therefore, advocates for a comprehensive and multifaceted rehabilitation approach that encompasses personal development, social reintegration, and ongoing support systems to address the underlying issues that contribute to criminal behavior.

Improving funding, staff training, jail facilities, and expanding livelihood programs all reflect the growing recognition that effective rehabilitation must address the full spectrum of a PDL's life. Creating more holistic and supportive environments within correctional systems, we can facilitate a smoother transition for individuals back into society, fostering not only personal growth but also the rebuilding of their social identity. This comprehensive approach is in line with contemporary rehabilitation theories, such as Welch's, which emphasized that rehabilitation should go beyond simply correcting behavior to focus on the overall transformation of the individual. It highlighted the importance of shaping new identities and fostering skills that allow former offenders to reintegrate as productive, law-abiding citizens. Such evolving correctional reform strategies recognize that long-term success in reducing recidivism hinges on a multi-faceted approach that incorporates personal development, societal reintegration, and sustained community support. These efforts aim not only to address the immediate issues

contributing to criminal behavior but also to promote lasting change by addressing the root causes of offending and offering individuals the tools they need for a successful future. Ultimately, the shift towards comprehensive, rehabilitative practices reflects a deeper understanding of the complexities of criminal behavior and the need for a more compassionate, forward-thinking approach to correctional reform.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Males between the ages of 32 and 38 make up the majority of PDLs in North Cotabato District Jails. Also, PDLs who are single make for about half of the population and special Laws are the most violated inside the North Cotabato District Jail Male and Female Dormitories.
2. The educational program is the most widely used of the three rehabilitation initiatives.
3. The prison has the least number of educational resources, including computers, books, and magazines.
4. The only demographic factor that significantly differs across the PDLs' rehabilitation programs is age.
5. There is a strong correlation between the degree of implementation and the severity of issues with PDL rehabilitation treatments.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher therefore recommends the following:

1. The Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) may utilize this study's findings to assess the strengths and weaknesses of rehabilitation programs in correctional facilities. This evaluation may guide the development of targeted policies aligned with national and international standards. Key recommendations include regular program outcome assessments, integration of gender-sensitive approaches, resource allocation to address gaps, and collaboration with experts to update and standardize rehabilitation frameworks for the evolving needs of PDLs.
2. It is recommended that the North Cotabato District Jail Male Dormitory may prioritize enhancing rehabilitation programs by tailoring them to the specific demographic profiles and needs of male inmates. Efforts may focus on strengthening educational, livelihood, and recreational programs to address challenges effectively, promote personal growth, and improve mental health. Additionally, regular assessments of program implementation and problem areas are essential to ensure the interventions remain relevant and impactful. Providing adequate resources, training staff, and fostering partnerships with external organizations may further support the successful reintegration of PDLs into society and help reduce recidivism.

3. It is recommended that the North Cotabato District Jail Female Dormitory develop gender-sensitive rehabilitation programs that specifically address the unique needs and challenges faced by female jail population. Policymakers and stakeholders may consider factors such as sex, age, and civil status when designing these programs to ensure they empower female jail population, enhance their well-being, and effectively prepare them for reintegration into society.
4. It is recommended that Holy Trinity College of General Santos City may be involved in supporting rehabilitation programs for PDLs. By understanding the demographic profile of PDLs, the school can tailor its educational and support services to address specific needs based on age, sex, civil status, and types of offense. Additionally, evaluating the implementation level and identifying problems in current rehabilitation programs allows the school to improve and optimize its involvement, whether in educational, livelihood, or recreational areas. The findings on significant differences based on demographics and the relationship between program implementation and encountered issues can guide the school in refining its strategies and ensuring more effective, equitable, and impactful rehabilitation initiatives for PDLs, promoting their reintegration into society and reducing recidivism.
5. It is recommended that rehabilitation programs for PDLs be enhanced to ensure their access to humanitarian treatment. By prioritizing investments in rehabilitation efforts, correctional facilities may adopt a more compassionate and effective approach to addressing criminal behavior. Tailoring these programs to better prepare PDLs for reintegration into society will foster successful life changes, reduce recidivism, and promote a more equitable approach to justice. Additionally, regular assessments of rehabilitation programs may be conducted to ensure their continuous improvement and alignment with international human rights standards.
6. It is recommended that the researcher continues to assess and improve rehabilitation programs for PDLs to ensure they meet their needs. Policymakers should focus on developing gender-sensitive programs that consider the different challenges faced by each group. Additionally, increasing resource allocation and personnel training may help enhance the effectiveness of these programs. Continuous evaluation and adaptation of rehabilitation strategies will contribute to better outcomes for PDLs.
7. It is recommended that future researchers build upon the findings of this study to explore the effectiveness of rehabilitation programs for PDLs in various correctional facilities. Research may further investigate gender-specific needs and challenges, as well as the spiritual and therapeutic modalities that impact rehabilitation success. Additionally, include the PDLs civil status of being separated that may affect them.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher made sure to follow all ethical guidelines set by Holy Trinity College to ensure that no practices were used that could potentially harm or exploit those involved in the study.

Informed Consent: The researcher gave a thorough written and verbal explanation of the study's objectives and purpose before to administering the survey. After verbally agreeing, participants were asked to sign a formal permission form. The researcher felt that because the respondents voluntarily participated, they need to be fully informed of the results and conclusions of the study and be acknowledged for their participation.

Voluntary Participation: The researcher made sure that the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) were provided with clear, thorough, and voluntary informed consent, ensuring they fully understood the study's purpose, scope, and any potential risks before agreeing to take part. This process included offering detailed explanations of the study's objectives, methods, and steps taken to protect their privacy and confidentiality.

Data Privacy. The PDLs were informed beforehand that all data would be destroyed once the analysis was complete. They were assured that their identities would remain confidential, and a coding system would be used to protect their personal information. The PDLs were also given the option to include their names on the questionnaire if they chose to do so.

Gender Sensitivity. By integrating gender-sensitive ethical considerations into research practices, researchers can uphold foundational principles such as respect, justice, and integrity, ensuring that all individuals, regardless of gender, were treated with dignity and fairness. This commitment to gender sensitivity helps challenge stereotypes, reduce biases, and empower underrepresented groups, ultimately fostering a more equitable and just society. Furthermore, it laid the foundation for transformative social change, as research that is mindful of gender considerations was better positioned to inform policies and practices that supported the well-being and rights of all people, irrespective of their gender identity or background.

Cultural Sensitivity. It refers to the ability to recognize, understand, and respect the unique attributes and needs associated with diverse cultures, acknowledging that cultural differences can significantly influence individuals' perspectives, behaviors, and interactions. This cultural competence challenges the planning and implementation of activities by highlighting the importance of ensuring that all participants, including PDLs, have equal opportunities for involvement, regardless of their cultural backgrounds. This involved designing inclusive programs and interventions that are sensitive to the varied cultural norms, traditions, and values of PDLs, creating an environment that fosters mutual respect and understanding.

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